

D1.1

Legal, Regulative and Ethical Requirements for EOSC Secure Data Sharing and Processing

06/11/2024

Title	D1.1 Legal, Regulative and Ethical Requirements for EOSC Secure Data Sharing and Processing
Document description	The deliverable D1.1. is a report outlining the method for determining the legal, regulatory, and ethical requirements for European Open Science Platform (EOSC) secure data sharing and processing. The document outlines the project, the proposed technology components, and explains the desk research and consensus building process that led to the requirements gathering for the TITAN EOSC.
Deliverable Type	R: Report
Dissemination level	PU: Public
Status	D: Draft
Task	T1.1
Lead Partner	TRI
Partners Involved	CHA, INS, SAR, VEN, UEF, ZEN, FRA, UKO, UVC
Date	M9

Revision history	Author	Delivery date	Summary of changes and comments
Version 01	Robin Renwick, and Paula Cullen (TRI)	16-05-2024	V0.1 (first draft)
Version 02	Robin Renwick, and Paula Cullen (TRI)	28-07-2024	V0.2 (content structuring)
Version 03	Nikola Tomić, Krzysztof Garstka, Robin Renwick (TRI), Eduard Wolf (FRA), Volker Riediger, Julian Flake), Veronika Vasileva (UKO)	14-10-2024	V0.3 (first draft)
Version 04	Robin Renwick (TRI), Pegah Nikbakht Bideh (CAN), Ana Kovačević, Vladimir Urošević (ZEN), Sammy Oina (UVC)	24-10-2024	V0.4 (second draft)
Version 05	Robin Renwick and Nikola Tomic (TRI)	31-10-2024	V0.5 (pre-final draft)
Version 06	Robin Renwick and Nikola Tomic (TRI)	04-11-2024	V0.6 (TRI internal review)
Version 07	Eduard Wolf (FRA) and Jorge Silva (FUJ)	05-11-2024	V0.7 (FRA and FUJ review)
Final version	Robin Renwick (TRI)	06-11-2024	V1.0 (final draft)

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A software platform solution for confidential data collaboration
& secure and privacy-preserving data processing

Grant Agreement No: 101129822
Call: HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01
Topic: HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-06
Type of action: HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

List of Figures	5
List of Tables	6
List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	7
Executive Summary	9
1. Introduction	10
2. TITAN Project	11
2.1. Proposed technical components	11
2.1.1. Privacy-preserving identity management	12
2.1.2. Federated learning toolbox	12
2.1.3. Software support for confidential GPUs	12
2.1.4. Confidential computing system for AI	12
2.1.5. Confidential workload lifecycle manager	13
2.1.6. Secure decentralized data sharing	13
2.1.7. Sleep healthcare data analysis based on multi-party machine learning.....	13
2.1.8. Machine learning models for agriculture disease predictions and support-decisions system.....	14
2.1.9. Confidential computing for privacy-preserving multi-party machine learning based on TEEs	14
2.1.10. Data space connectors	14
2.1.11. Policy enforcement point and policy decision point	15
3. Requirements elicitation methodology	16
3.1. Preparation	16
3.1.1. Elicitation criteria.....	16
3.1.2. Requirement templates.....	18
3.1.3. Rules for TITAN requirements elicitation	22
3.2. Collection	25
3.3. Elicitation and analysis	26
4. Legal, regulatory, and ethical requirements collection process	27
4.1. Desk research	27
4.1.1. European regulations	27
4.1.2. National legislations	28
4.1.3. Complementary documents	28
4.1.4. Case study specific requirements	29
4.1.5. Ethical frameworks	29
4.2. Requirements overview	29
4.2.1. Summary of the requirements table	29
4.3. Full legal, regulatory, and ethical requirements table	32
5. Conclusions and next steps	34
Annex I	35

List of Figures

Figure 1. Functional MASTeR Template	19
Figure 2. Property MASTeR Template.....	20
Figure 3. Environment MASTeR Template	21
Figure 4. Process MASTeR Template	21
Figure 5. Logic MASTeR Template	21
Figure 6. Event MASTeR Template.....	22
Figure 7. Time MASTeR Template.....	22

List of Tables

Table 1. Overview of proposed architecture	11
Table 2. Non-Functional Requirement Categories.....	20
Table 3. Rules for Individual Requirements	23
Table 4. Forbidden Words.....	24
Table 5. Quality Goals for the Complete Requirement Set	25
Table 6. Requirements overview	29
Table 7. Requirements categorisation	30
Table 8. Requirements subject matter	31
Table 9. Requirements justification	32

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Explanation/ Definition
ABAC	Attribute Based Access Control
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CocosAI	Confidential Computing System for Artificial Intelligence
CC	Confidential Computing
CVM	Confidential Virtual Machine
DID	Decentralized Identifiers
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
DoA	Description of Action
EBSI	European Blockchain Services Infrastructure
EC	European Commission
EHDS	European Healthcare Data Space
EHR	Electronic Health Records
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-IF	European Open Science Cloud Interoperability Framework
FLT	Federated Learning Toolbox
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPU	Graphical Processor Unit
HAL	Hardware Abstraction Layer
IaC	Infrastructure-as-Code
IdM	Privacy preserving Identity Management
MASTeR	Mustergültige Anforderungen - die SOPHIST TEmplates für Requirements
ML	Machine Learning
OPA	Open Policy Agent
PO	European Commission Project Officer
PEP	Policy Enforcement Point
PDP	Policy Decision Point

RE	Requirements Engineering
SMPC	Secure Multi-Party Computation
SSI	Self-sovereign Identities
TEE	Trusted Execution Environments
TITAN	Trusted environments for confidential computing and secure data sharing
VC	Verifiable Credential
VP	Verifiable Presentation
VM	Virtual Machine
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WP	Work package
ZKP	Zero-Knowledge Proof

Executive Summary

This report represents deliverable D1.1 of the TITAN project, funded by the European Union, under Grant Agreement No. 101129822. It presents the initial version of the legal, regulative, and ethical requirements for the TITAN software platform solution for confidential data collaboration and secure and privacy-preserving data processing. The requirements were collected with the use cases and European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) needs in mind. These requirements complement the technical requirements described in D1.2 of the TITAN project.

Both deliverables are integral to all phases of the TITAN project, serving as main references for the design, development, and integration activities. The information presented in this deliverable is preliminary and will evolve throughout the project life cycle, expecting an updated release in M18.

Contributions from activities across other project work packages and tasks are expected to influence the living content of this document.

1. Introduction

This report represents deliverable D1.1 of the TITAN project, funded by the European Union, under Grant Agreement No. 101129822, entitled *D1.1 - Legal, Regulatory and Ethical Requirements for EOSC Secure Data Sharing and Processing*.

The report presents the initial version of the legal, regulatory, and ethical requirements for the TITAN software platform. The TITAN platform is designed and developed for confidential data collaboration and secure and privacy-preserving data processing, compatible with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

The requirements were collected considering the use cases, and will iterate until M18. The legal, regulatory, and ethical requirements presented in this deliverable complement the technical requirements described in *D1.2 - Technical requirements for EOSC secure data sharing and processing* of the TITAN project, also delivered in M9.

The information presented in this deliverable is preliminary, and will evolve through the project life cycle, expecting an updated release in M18. The report is structured in five sections, as follows:

- Section 1 is currently being read and provides the introduction to the report.
- Section 2 provides an overview of the TITAN project, including its goals and overarching vision. It also provides a short introduction to the technological components of the TITAN architecture. This includes an introduction to each of the technological assets' functions, implementation, and interoperability plans. More detail on the technical components, proposed project architecture and pilot case studies is provided in D1.2 on technical, functional and non-functional requirements.
- Section 3 provides an overview of the requirements gathering methodology. It provides explanations for why the MASTeR method was chosen, and the steps required to deploy this methodology into the TITAN requirement engineering process. This section also includes information on the rules that were followed during the requirements elicitation phase.
- Section 4 provides specific information regarding the Legal, Regulatory, and Ethical requirements for the TITAN project. This includes an overview of the process, and an overview of the resources analysed. This section provides a summary of the requirements table, including a breakdown of gathered requirements by type, category, subject matter, and justification. Finally, the section introduces the full Legal, Regulatory, and Ethical requirements table (which resides in Annex I). The requirements contained within the Annex allow the reader to browse the full list of Legal, Regulatory, and Ethical requirements. The table is presented before the refinement process has begun, as is correct as at 24/10/2024 (M9). It is intended that the list will be refined by all partners, with support and guidance from UKO over the next months of the project.
- Section 5 provides a short conclusion to the report and outlines next steps.
- Annex I provides the full list of Legal, Regulatory and Ethical requirements, correct as of 24/10/2024 (M9).

2. TITAN Project

The TITAN (Trusted environments for confidential computing and secure data sharing) project will enhance the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) with a software platform that enables secure and privacy-preserving access to sensitive datasets from government, public, and private entities. The project supports compliance objectives against the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and other relevant regulations, such as the Data Act, AI Act, and European Digital Identity Framework.

Addressing the significant security risks associated with data sharing, TITAN employs innovative solutions such as Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) for confidential data processing, reliable data anonymization, and decentralized blockchain-based access control. The platform will be demonstrated in cross-border public administration and healthcare scenarios, and it will be designed to be compatible with the EOSC Interoperability Framework (IF) by leveraging privacy-enhancing technologies and distributed ledger technologies for transparent access management. TITAN aims to support European scientific excellence through secure and compliant data collaboration. More information about TITAN can be found on the dedicated website: <https://titan-eosc.eu>.

2.1. Proposed technical components

Below is an overview of the technical components of the TITAN platform, as provided by the technical partners in the project.

Table 1. Overview of proposed architecture

NAME	PARTNER	Existing TRL
Privacy-preserving identity management with W3C verifiable credentials	UMU	3
	UMU	3
Federated learning toolbox	ZEN	4
Software support for Confidential GPUs	CAB	2
Confidential computing system for AI	UVC	4
Confidential workload lifecycle manager	CAB	4
Secure decentralized data sharing	ZEN, UVC	3
Sleep healthcare data analysis based on multi-party machine learning	CHA, INS, UEF	4
Machine learning models for agriculture disease predictions and support-decisions system	ITA	5
Confidential computing for privacy-preserving multi-party machine learning based on Trusted Execution Environments	UVC	3
Data space connectors	UMU	3
Policy enforcement point and policy decision point	FUJ	4

2.1.1. Privacy-preserving identity management

Privacy-preserving Identity Management (IdM) with W3C Verifiable Credentials enables users to securely manage and store their identity information while maintaining control over their privacy (self-sovereign identities). Self-sovereign Identities (SSI) will be the IdM solution used in the data connector of the data sharing platform.

Utilizing Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs) and Verifiable Credentials (VCs), individuals can authenticate and prove attributes without revealing unnecessary data. Additionally, cryptographic solutions like Zero-Knowledge Proof (ZKP) are addressed for selective disclosure.

Furthermore, sticky policies will be integrated with w3c VC to ensure that data usage rules persist with the data as it is shared across different entities. These policies are embedded within the credential, specifying how the data can be used, stored, and shared. When a verifier requests the credential, they must adhere to these policies, ensuring user consent and control are maintained. This approach enhances privacy and compliance with data protection regulations by enforcing consistent data handling practices. Users benefit from transparency and trust, knowing their data usage preferences are respected throughout its lifecycle.

2.1.2. Federated learning toolbox

Federated Learning Toolbox (FLT) implements the secure orchestration of decentralized Machine Learning (ML) workloads processing in TITAN. It enables collaborative ML, general data analysis, and decoupling of confidential data from the model training without central posting of the datasets, using a secure node and cloud infrastructure. Nodes receive workloads from the server and execute them by downloading the requested container images. The container accesses the local data through the node and executes algorithms with the given parameters. This way the sensitive datasets never leave the origin local-hosted premises (hospital datacentres in the Use Case 2 example, supporting compliance efforts), but the algorithms get deployed towards the data in federated compute-to-data mode (optionally in TEE via a secure channel), achieving insights or training models with the Intellectual Property (IP) they contain remaining protected on the edge.

2.1.3. Software support for confidential GPUs

GPUs can complete simple and repetitive tasks much faster because it can break the task down into smaller components and finish them in parallel. To preserve the confidentiality and integrity of such tasks and processings, confidential GPUs are required. GPU confidential computing solutions rely on a confidential virtual machine (CVM) trusted execution environment (TEE) on the CPU, enabled by SEV-SNP on AMD CPUs or by TDX 1.x on Intel CPUs.

2.1.4. Confidential computing system for AI

Confidential Computing System for AI (CocosAI) is a SW system for enabling confidential and privacy-preserving AI/ML, i.e. execution of model training and algorithm inference on

confidential data sets. Privacy-preservation is considered a “holy grail” of AI. It opens many possibilities, among which is a collaborative, trustworthy AI. CocosAI leverages Confidential Computing, a novel paradigm based on specialized HW CPU extensions for producing secure encrypted enclaves in memory (Trusted Execution Environments, or TEEs), thus isolating confidential data and programs from the rest of the SW running on the host. The final product enables data scientists to train AI and ML models on confidential data that is never revealed and can be used for Secure Multi-Party Computation (SMPC). AI/ML on combined data sets that come from different sources will unlock huge value.

2.1.5. Confidential workload lifecycle manager

Tower is an orchestration service to automate the deployment of Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) infrastructure resources. It strictly follows Infrastructure-as-Code (IaC) and cloud security best practices, putting end users firmly in control of their setups. It offers a set of open-source Terraform configurations to help you manage and provision highly secure runtime environments on a wide set of public cloud providers, on-premises, or bare-metal setups. Tower accepts end-user's requirements including but not limited to the target cloud provider, the hardware platform (Intel TDX, AMD SNP) with or without GPU support, the VM family and size, and specific end-user's environment policy. It then deploys a TEE automatically via Infrastructure as Code configurations. Lifecycle management activities such as updates, patches and changes are controlled by the end-user and can be applied automatically to the execution environments.

2.1.6. Secure decentralized data sharing

A blockchain-based secure data exchange infrastructure platform with zero-knowledge proofs, encryption-supported Smart Contracts and Decentralized IDs (DIDs) is to be coupled with (currently used or future EOSC-adopted) Verifiable Credentials (VCs). Modules for managing DIDs and Self-Sovereign Identifiers (SSIs) generate and administer decentralised identities, using verifiable credentials to confirm data sources and their composition without revealing any data structure or content.

The solution utilises an open-source, lightweight, high-performance community-supported DLT infrastructure, ensuring full traceability, permanent storage, and management of smart contracts, potentially also including the storage of all crucial metadata pertaining to each collaborative computation workload execution (audit log information, remote attestation report, etc.) for added security and verifiability.

2.1.7. Sleep healthcare data analysis based on multi-party machine learning

Computer codes for calculation of new diagnostic parameters (obstruction severity, obstruction duration, desaturation severity, desaturation duration, and adjusted-AHI) considering the number, duration, and morphology of individual breathing cessation events.

Computer codes of neural network-based estimation of the apnea-hypopnea index, multiple sleep latency test outcome, sleep structure (sleep stages) from PSG and HSAT signals.

Computer codes for automatic exportation and pseudonymization of polysomnographic data from various commercial PSG software.

Computer codes for automatic calculation of various metrics from blood oxygen saturation and photoplethysmography signals.

2.1.8. Machine learning models for agriculture disease predictions and support-decisions system

License for using the services providing access to the data sets (climatic data and derived data, Copernicus images and derived data, Spanish registry data - rustic parcels-, etc.), transforming data set functionalities, and predictions models.

2.1.9. Confidential computing for privacy-preserving multi-party machine learning based on TEEs

The Confidential Computing (CC) module of the TITAN EOSC platform is critical for enabling secure and privacy-preserving multi-party machine learning. This module establishes a robust basis for collaborative AI applications that use Trusted Execution Environments (TEE).

At the core of everything is the TEE Manager, responsible for dynamically deploying and configuring the TEEs. The TEE Manager will oversee the execution and health of the secure enclaves, ensuring that data confidentiality is maintained throughout the process. When a calculation is finished, it securely destroys TEEs and deletes all associated data.

The TEE Manager is accompanied by an In-Enclave Agent, which is lightweight software that runs within the secure enclave. The In-Enclave Agent manages algorithm execution and enables secure data transmission between clients over TLS-encrypted channels. The In-Enclave Agent also performs remote attestation, which verifies the integrity and authenticity of the execution environment.

This is supported by the Hardware Abstraction Layer (HAL), which provides a standard API for interacting with various hardware designs, including AMD SEV and Intel TDX. The HAL isolates hardware specifics, allowing for simple integration and resource management efficiency in secret computing operations.

The remote attestation mechanism leverages TEEs to ensure the remote system's integrity. This ensures that data and workloads are run in trusted and separated contexts, even in untrusted settings, hence boosting overall security and confidentiality.

Additionally, the CC component supports a variety of runtime environments, including Python, Docker, and WebAssembly. This adaptability enables the secure and confidential execution of a wide range of AI and machine learning computations.

2.1.10. Data space connectors

Data space connectors enable secure and compliant data exchange between different systems, ensuring interoperability and privacy. They use technologies like Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs) and Verifiable Credentials (VCs) to give users control over their data and ensure that privacy policies are enforced.

The FIWARE Data Space Connector is a suite of components that any organization participating in a data space should deploy to connect to that space. It implements recommendations from the Data Spaces Business Alliance (DSBA) as they evolve, ensuring up-to-date alignment with best practices. This connector integrates with trust services aligned with European Blockchain Services Infrastructure (EBSI) specifications, supporting authentication via W3C DIDs and Verifiable Credentials/Presentations (VC/VP), using SIOPv2 and OIDC4VP protocols.

It also provides attribute-based access control (ABAC) through XACML architecture, leveraging ODRL and Open Policy Agent (OPA) for managing permissions. Additionally, it is compatible with the ETSI NGSI-LD API for data exchange but can also be adapted to other RESTful APIs by modifying or extending its Policy Decision Point (PDP) component. This ensures flexibility in handling different types of API integrations, including support for TMForum APIs to manage contract negotiations. The FIWARE Data Space Connector can be deployed easily on Kubernetes environments, ensuring scalable and flexible integration across entities.

2.1.11. Policy enforcement point and policy decision point

This tool is composed by a Policy Enforcement Point (PEP) and a Policy Decision Point (PDP). The PEP oversees communicating with the user that makes a query for an accessing to a resource and make an action. The PDP is the one which makes the real decision, the user asks for the access and the PDP applies some policies and criterion to know if the user is suitable to make the requested action in the resource.

3. Requirements elicitation methodology

The requirements elicitation process for TITAN was built upon scientific and practical knowledge in requirements engineering. The process consists of the following three steps:

1. **Preparation.** Definition of common elicitation criteria, templates, and quality goals
2. **Collection.** Capturing non-functional and functional requirements from stakeholder perspective
3. **Elicitation and analysis.** Quality assurance and consolidation of preliminary requirement lists

Steps 2 and 3 are an interactive process between partners, the system use case providers, and the asset providers to determine the user and system requirements. Requirements are collected, classified, prioritised, and specified. These steps are repeated until all requirements are collected and the participants are satisfied with the result.

3.1. Preparation

The first phase of the requirements elicitation process in TITAN is the preparation phase. In this phase, UKO, as requirements engineering expert, defined criteria and provided a template for requirements elicitation as well as a 'cheat sheet' with all the rules for understanding the criteria and formulating the requirements. Both were presented to the partners involved in WP1 and complemented by ideas from partners. In addition, further ambiguities were clarified in partner discussions during the regular bi-weekly WP1 meetings. Thus, a common understanding was achieved.

3.1.1. Elicitation criteria

For TITAN's requirements elicitation the following criteria and attributes were defined and provided as a legend to all partners. A definition table is provided in Table 6.

Requirement ID

The unique requirement ID for reference and traceability purposes.

Type

The type of the requirement is one of *legal*, *ethical*, *functional*, *property/environment*, *non-functional*, or *process*. Legal requirements are referring to regulations and law. Technical requirements are encompassing functional and non-functional requirements. Thereby, functional requirements may define system functionality, interactions between components, interactions to achieve user goals, and others. Further, they may refer to implementation technologies or data formats, APIs or pre-existing services that can be utilized in TITAN.

In addition, non-functional requirements can also be so-called meta requirements of type *document*. Meta requirements address the form and structure of the individual requirements and the documentation. Meta requirements are fulfilled by the requirements documents

themselves, in contrast to ordinary requirements that are to be fulfilled by the system's realisation.

Category

The focus of a requirement is defined by its category. According to ISO/IEC 25010:2023 Systems and software engineering — Systems and software Quality Requirements and Evaluation (SQuaRE) — Product quality model¹, the main categories used in the requirements elicitation process are functional suitability, performance, efficiency, compatibility, interaction capability, reliability, security, maintainability, flexibility, and safety. For TITAN's requirements, the partners identified the following categories:

- Authentication & Authorization
- Automation
- Data Agreement
- Data Discovery
- Data Sharing
- Documentation
- Documentation Content / IPR
- Documentation Content / Security
- Efficiency
- Feature
- Federated Learning
- General Requirements
- Interoperability
- Metadata
- Monitoring & Traceability
- Network
- Non-linear Operations
- Performance & Sustainability
- Requirement Content
- Scalability
- Security
- Security & Maintainability
- Security & Privacy
- Security/Logging
- Technical
- Usability
- User Interface

Liability

The liability is one of *SHALL*, *SHOULD* or *WILL*. The liabilities are explained in section 3.3.1.

Priority

The priority of the requirement can be either *high*, *medium*, or *low*. In addition to the liability, the priority gives hints to the realisation order. High priority requirements are requirements

¹ ISO/IEC 25010:2023 Systems and software engineering — Systems and software Quality Requirements and Evaluation (SQuaRE) — Product quality model, available at: <https://www.iso.org/standard/78176.html>

that must be implemented at first, medium priority requirements are recommended to be developed after the high priority ones, and low priority requirements are requirements which provide a certain additive value to the system, but their fulfilment is not crucial in the beginning.

Subject Matter

The subject matter is the name of the system, subsystem, or actor, which is the subject of the requirements sentence.

Requirement Sentence

A single concrete sentence in the form of one of the MASTeR templates.

Justification

The justification documents the reason the requirement is relevant for the project, e.g., GDPR, EOSC-IF.

Refers To

References to other documents and applicable standards, as specific as possible.

Author

The name of the author (partner acronym) of the requirement.

Responsible Task

The task numbers of the responsible TITAN tasks that contribute to the realisation and fulfilment of the requirement.

Source (Stakeholder)

Sources are names of stakeholders for which the requirements are relevant.

Comments

Additional comments contain any additional information that is valuable to understand the requirement.

3.1.2. Requirement templates

In general, requirements quality improves when clear rules for the formulation of the requirements are defined and followed. To support this, template systems to structure the requirement descriptions are used.

In TITAN, requirements follow the so-called Sophist MASTeR templates that have emerged from knowledge and experience in a wide range of projects. MASTeR is a German acronym for "Mustergültige Anforderungen - die SOPHIST TEmplates für Requirements", in English "Immaculate requirements - the SOPHIST TEmplates for Requirements". The brief summary of the template system in this section explains its purpose and application.

There is a basic template for functional requirements as well as three templates for non-functional requirements. The latter are meant for property, environment, and process requirements. These templates can be extended by an optional part for logical, event, and

time related conditions. When the template system does not fit all project needs, it can be extended. So far, in TITAN no extension was necessary.

In addition to the templates, a set of rules gives hints for creating understandable and unambiguous requirements of high quality. The templates and rules are explained in the following.

3.1.2.1. Functional MASTeR

The MASTeR template system follows simple syntactical rules for the requirements sentences. For example, in the Functional MASTeR template in Fig. 1, the parts in capital letters are keywords that appear in the sentence. Parts in square brackets [...] are optional, and parts in angular brackets <...> must be replaced.

Figure 1. Functional MASTeR Template

Each sentence must contain one of the liability keywords SHALL (mandatory), SHOULD (optional), or WILL (mandatory, but realized in future).

Functional requirements according to Figure. 1 come in three flavours. We will give examples from TITAN for each.

1. Independent System Activities (path "-")

Describes activities of the system that are executed autonomously without user interaction.

Example: *The system SHALL apply an authentication and authorisation solution that could be federated.*

2. User Interaction (path "PROVIDE...")

Describes functionality that require user interaction. The system enables users to perform a function to achieve a goal.

Example: *The authentication system SHALL PROVIDE the users THE ABILITY TO choose the specific data that will be shared during an authentication and authorization process.*

3. Interface Requirements (path "BE ABLE TO")

Describes requirements that deal with integration of external systems.

Example: *The system SHALL BE ABLE TO maintain access to the blockchain network.*

Non-Functional Requirements

The remaining three basic templates are used to formulate non-functional requirements. They describe system properties, the system's operating environment, and requirements for

the development and maintenance process. Table 2 shows several types of non-functional requirements and the applicable template.

Table 2. Non-Functional Requirement Categories

	Content	Property MASTeR	Environment MASTeR	Process MASTeR
Quality Requirements	Qualitative property of the system of interest (performance requirement)	X		
Technological Requirements	Efficient way to give more accuracy to the scope of a system functionality	X	Environmental Requirements Quantity Requirements	
User Interface Requirements	Details of the visual and acoustic presentation of the user functionality	X		
Requirements for other components	Installation and deployment requirements, tools for assembling components	X		
Requirements for Activities to be carried out	Requirements for the development and operation process of the system	X		X
Legal and Contractual Requirements	Agreed rights and legal frameworks that apply to the development and usage of the system	X		X

3.1.2.2. Property MASTeR

Figure 2. Property MASTeR Template

Property requirements denote quality and performance criteria that the system has to fulfil. Example: *The response time of the user interface SHOULD BE less than 5 seconds.*

3.1.2.3. Environment MASTeR

Figure 3. Environment MASTeR Template

Environmental requirements describe conditions that the system and its execution environment must meet.

Example: *The system SHALL BE DESIGNED IN A WAY that the Trusted Execution Environment CAN BE OPERATED on virtual machines with at least 4GB of main memory.*

3.1.2.4. Process MASTeR

Figure 4. Process MASTeR Template

Process requirements define obligations of the development, deployment, and maintenance of the system.

Example: *The data providers SHALL define usage policies that comply to the data protection regulations of the originating country.*

3.1.2.5. Conditional MASTeR templates

The optional condition parts may be added to address logical, event, and time restrictions. The respective templates are shown here to complete the template definitions. Currently, these conditions are not used in TITAN requirements. The three types of conditional templates are shown in Figure. 5 to Figure. 7.

Figure 5. Logic MASTeR Template

Figure 6. Event MASTeR Template

Figure 7. Time MASTeR Template

3.1.3. Rules for TITAN requirements elicitation

The requirements elicitation in TITAN was conducted by an initial agreement on common rules and criteria. The rules are divided into two groups: rules for individual requirements, and rules for the complete requirement set. These rules are shown in the rest of this section. Many of the rules represent best-practice requirements engineering knowledge, others are quality criteria from international requirements engineering standards like ISO/IEC/IEEE 29148:2018 Systems and software engineering – Life cycle processes – Requirements engineering.²

3.1.3.1. Rules and quality goals for individual requirements

Each requirement has to be complete with respect to the criteria and attributes that were described in Section 3.2.

Table 3 shows additional rules for individual requirements. The rules were taken from the “SOPHIST REgelwerk” for Requirements Engineering.³ These rules are listed in Table 3. They were applied in TITAN to achieve high-quality requirements. Additionally, Table 4 lists forbidden words that are known to introduce ambiguities or misunderstandings, and that may lead to requirements that cannot be tested and validated.

² ISO/IEC/IEEE 29148:2018 Systems and software engineering – Life cycle processes – Requirements engineering, available at: <https://www.iso.org/standard/72089.html>

³ C. Rupp and SOPHIST GmbH, *Requirements-Engineering und -Management – Aus der Praxis von klassisch bis agil*, 7th ed. Carl Hanser Verlag München, 2020

Table 3. Rules for Individual Requirements

Rule #	Priority	Rule	Description
1	Medium	Write every requirement in active voice	Passive voice can delete agents (persons or systems). Add missing agents.
2	Medium	Express every process using unambiguous main verbs.	Imprecise main verbs mask the desired functionality. Chose a verb that expresses the functionality precisely.
3	High	Resolve nominalisations that are not exactly defined and write one or several new requirements with a "good" main verb for every nominalisation.	A nominalisation can mask an entire process. Is this process not sufficiently specified, create new additional requirements with suitable main verbs.
4	Low	Dissolve light-verb constructions and define the required process, which represents the system's behaviour using a "good" main verb.	A light-verb construction can mask an entire process. Chose a verb that expresses the desired functionality precisely.
5	Medium	Write exactly one requirement statement for each main verb.	Create new requirements for every additional main verb.
6	High	Identify missing Information around the main verb.	Ask the typical 5Ws + 1H (Who, What, When, Where, Why, How) and add missing information.
7	Medium	Identify missing Information around the properties (adjectives/adverbs).	Ask the typical 5Ws + 1H (Who, What, When, Where, Why, How) and add missing information. If the corresponding process is not described sufficiently create a new requirement with a suitable main verb.
8	Medium	Word properties measurable and testable.	Comparative degrees and superlatives always need a reference point.
9	Low	Formulate separate requirements for non-functional aspects if these aspects are independent or needed as a constraint for several functionalities.	Separate the non-functional aspect, if it should be handled independently OR if it is desired comprehensively for several requirements
10	Medium	Analyse numbers and quantities.	Required functions or properties must be applicable to all items of the given portion and no others. If this is not the case, the portion has either to be expanded or restricted.

			Exceptions must be specified additionally.
11	Medium	Identify missing numbers and quantities.	For every required function or property, the group of items has to be defined for which it is applicable.
12	High	Analyse ambiguous nouns.	Ambiguous nouns describe a group of items or actors that is not distinct. Specify them more precisely.
13	Low	Replace formulations that describe possible or impossible situations	Requirements on the possibility or impossibility of functions delete the business logic behind. Identify and add the missing business logic.
14	Low	Remove subordinate clauses that contain irrelevant information for the requirement meaning.	Motivations and other additional information should be added as comment, not as part of the requirement sentence.
15	Low	Shorten or eliminate flowery expressions or phrases that are irrelevant for your requirement.	Shorten or eliminate flowery expressions or phrases that are irrelevant for your requirement.
16	Medium	Analyse exceptions to the usual behaviour of the system and extend the requirement respective write an additional requirement.	Not only the normal behaviour has to be described, but also the behaviour in exception state.
17	High	Requirements with incomplete conditional structures should be checked and formulated or described by another requirement.	Describe the systems behaviour also for the state that the condition is not fulfilled.
18	High	Write one or more requirements for every implicit assumption not described.	Descriptions can contain implicit assumptions that are preconditions to the description. Key words that indicate implicit assumptions are, for example, temporal or logic processes, or nouns with related describing words. Is an implicit assumption present, which is not described at another point, it has to be defined.

Table 4. Forbidden Words

"and/or", "and", "or"	"minimize"	"satisfactory"
"etc."	"maximize"	"adequate"
"goal"	"typical"	"quick"
"shall be included but not limited to"	"rapid"	"first rate"

“relevant”	“user-friendly”	“best possible”
“necessary”	“easy”	“great”
“appropriate”	“sufficient”	“small”
“as far as possible”	“enough”	“large”
“optimize”	“suitable”	“state of the art”

3.1.3.2. Quality goals for the complete requirement set

In addition to the rules for individual requirements, there are quality criteria for the whole requirements list. These cannot be checked on a single requirement, but only when considering the complete requirement set. Table 5 shows these goals. Requirements that give rise to improvements with respect to the goals were identified and marked to be fixed in the second iteration of TITAN’s RE process.

Table 5. Quality Goals for the Complete Requirement Set

Quality Goal	Description
Unique IDs	Each requirement in the TITAN requirements list (D1.1 and D1.2) shall have a unique requirement ID that can be used for reference in other documents, in related requirements, and in realisation artefacts to establish traceability links (e.g., source code, configuration files, deployment descriptors, etc.). Traceability ensures that every realisation artefact can be found easily when a change to the requirement occurs.
No Redundancy	Each requirement shall describe exactly one aspect of the system, and each aspect shall be described in exactly one requirement. This avoids duplicates and overlapping requirements that can lead to misunderstandings.
No Conflicts	Conflicting requirements may exist in the requirements list. They shall be clearly identified and refer to each other. At the latest, when a realisation decision is taken, one of the conflicting requirements must be selected and the others marked as not (longer) relevant.
Completeness	Completeness means that the requirements shall mention all cases and alternatives, even if some of them will not be realized. This can also be in a form that inapplicable alternatives are at least mentioned and documented. This minimises the likelihood of key facts being overlooked. This goal may be hard to achieve in the first iteration of the RE process. Nevertheless, incompleteness can be identified and fixed for the final requirements list.

3.2. Collection

The second phase of the requirements elicitation process is the collection phase. In this phase, various partners involved in WP1 provided requirements according to their expertise, domain knowledge, or use-case.

Furthermore, the phase was divided into collecting legal requirements, and non-technical and technical requirements.

Within bi-weekly meetings, UKO supported the partners and provided relevant feedback to their contributions.

A structured approach ensured the efficient collection of both legal and technical requirements. To achieve this, we utilized a variety of data sources. Regular meetings promoted collaboration and provided feedback amongst partners and stakeholders. The steps followed were:

- **Desk Research:** We start by conducting literature reviews, which include references detailed in the TITAN Grant Agreement, relevant legal frameworks, academic journal paper, conference papers and articles, industry reports, and similar publicly available documents from libraries, websites, journals, and policy initiatives. This step helped us identify applicable standards, legislations, and frameworks.
- **Best Practices:** We draw upon best practices from previous projects (TANGO), recognized industry standards (e.g., ISO), applicable legislative frameworks (e.g., GDPR, Data Act, etc), and technical guidelines such as the EOSC Interoperability Framework (EOSC IF). This ensures that requirements are both realistic and support compliance with current regulations.

3.3. Elicitation and analysis

The third and final phase was elicitation of legal, regulatory, ethical requirements and the elicitation of technical requirements. It is to be noted that the results in this deliverable only represent the first iteration of TITAN's requirements engineering process.

Technical requirements were delivered through T1.2 - Technical Requirements for EOSC Secure Data Sharing and Processing, led by UKO. For more details, please see the deliverable associated with that task, *D1.2. Technical requirements for EOSC secure data sharing and processing* (M9).

The final requirements list will be delivered M18, and developed by partners through an iterative process.

The purpose of the elicitation and analysis is quality assurance with respect to the rules formulated in Section 3.4. After initial requirements collection, the resulting raw list was frozen in order for task lead, UKO, to review the results and provide feedback to partners.

In case of inconsistencies or rule violations, identified requirements were pushed back to the author(s) for revision. Then, the resulting requirements list was compiled and again frozen.

The list was uploaded to <https://zenodo.org/records/13990809>. The full list of frozen requirements, as at 25/10/2024 (M9), are printed in this deliverable for documentation purposes and may be found in Annex I.

As a reader of this document, please keep in mind that it only represents a snapshot of a "living" list that will receive updates during the second iteration of the RE process.

4. Legal, regulative, and ethical requirements collection process

The TITAN Grant Agreement requires the consortium to determine Legal, Regulatory and Ethical Requirements for EOSC Secure Data Sharing and Processing (T1.1). The process for this will be outlined in the sections below.

4.1. Desk research

The task description outlines several legal frameworks from which the legal and regulatory requirements should be gathered such as: the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the Proposal for a Regulation on the European Healthcare Data Space (EHDS), the Data Act, the Data Governance Act, as well as requirements that stem from broad supporting frameworks such as the FAIR Data Principles report.

The consortium conducted a desk research exercise to establish which regulations and legal frameworks were applicable to the TITAN project. This drew on partner expertise, experience from various European projects, and the knowledge of the consortium with respect to the emerging data sharing and cybersecurity regulations. This was supplemented with regulations concerning blockchain and DLT, Artificial Intelligence, and digital identity, as the TITAN system contains specific components that are relevant to those regulations.

4.1.1. European regulations

At a European level several regulatory frameworks were included for analysis. From this analysis task leader TRI defined a set of distinct legal requirements. The regulatory frameworks were chosen due to their applicability to the EOSC platform development. The chosen regulatory frameworks were:

- General Data Protection Regulation⁴
- Proposal for a Regulation on a European Health Data Space⁵
 - including interoperability requirements for Electronic Health Records (EHR)
- Data Act⁶
- Data Governance Act⁷

⁴ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) (Text with EEA relevance), available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>

⁵ For more information, including the most recent 'compromise text', please see: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/>

⁶ Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2023 on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data and amending Regulation (EU) 2017/2394 and Directive (EU) 2020/1828 (Data Act) (Text with EEA relevance), available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/2854>

⁷ For more information, please see: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-governance-act-explained>

- Artificial Intelligence Act⁸
- Proposal for the Cyber Resilience Act⁹
- European Digital Identity Framework¹⁰

4.1.2. National legislations

At the time of submission of D1.1. (October 2024, M9 of the project), the table of requirements does not include national legislation. The reasons for this are the following:

- 1) WP1 does not have sufficient resources and duration to cover the legislation of all 27 member states (MS) of the EU in the first nine months of the project. The geographical and use case scoping of the TITAN project is primarily done as part of the architecture development in WP2.
- 2) WP2 on the technical architecture of the TITAN project began in M6 and the project partners are still deciding how TITAN will be used in the EOSC. This has implications to what type of uses and in what geographical scope the TITAN technological solutions will be deployed. Following this scoping exercise, WP1 partners will be able to identify the relevant countries and areas relevant for requirements gathering and include those specific national requirements to the list by M18.

4.1.3. Complementary documents

The complementary documents that were analysed included:

- FAIR Principles¹¹
- European Open Science Cloud Interoperability Framework¹²
- European Interoperability Framework¹³
- Prior project experience and lessons learned (TANGO¹⁴, TRUSTEE¹⁵)

⁸ Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act) (Text with EEA relevance), available at: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1689/oj>

⁹ Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on horizontal cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements and amending Regulation (EU) 2019/1020, available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52022PC0454>

¹⁰ Regulation (EU) 2024/1183 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 April 2024 amending Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 as regards establishing the European Digital Identity Framework, available at: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1183/oj>

¹¹ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

¹² European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Corcho, O., Eriksson, M., Kurowski, K., Ojsteršek, M. et al., *EOSC interoperability framework - Report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Groups FAIR and Architecture*, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/620649>

¹³ <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/nifo-national-interoperability-framework-observatory/european-interoperability-framework-detail>

¹⁴ Project TANGO, Horizon Europe, Grant Agreement, No. 101070052, More information available at: <https://tango-project.eu/>

¹⁵ Project TRUSTEE, Horizon Europe, Grant Agreement, No. 101070214, More information available at: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101070214>

4.1.4. Case study specific requirements

The two case studies of the TITAN project informed the development of the legal, ethical, and regulatory requirements.

The first use case originates from the public sector, the second from the healthcare domain. Further analysis is required to understand the ethical implications of these use cases, and will be conducted through the project's impact assessment process. This will culminate in a series of ethical requirements that will form part of the final requirements list for the TITAN platform. These requirements will be gathered by lead partner TRI, with support from the use case owners.

4.1.5. Ethical frameworks

The ethical frameworks considered were:

- High-Level Expert Group on AI presented Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence¹⁶

Consideration was also given to wider European codes of conduct, such as:

- EU Cloud Code of Conduct¹⁷

4.2. Requirements overview

Using the methodology outlined in Section 3, we were able to gather, adapt and categorise more than 180 requirements, in total, for the development and operation of TITAN's technical outputs.

Below a summary of the requirements are provided, describing supplementary information (e.g., type, category, subject matter, legal justification/source, etc) and commenting on any emerging patterns.

The full table with all requirements and categorisations can be found in Section 4 of this document.

4.2.1. Summary of the requirements table

Types - we've established four main, top-level types of requirements - functional, non-functional, legal, and documentation. Functional type denotes a requirement tied to the technology and its core function; non-functional indicates a connection to the wider environment within which technology persists. The types can overlap, to an extent - for example, there might be a legal requirement influencing a functional one; documentation might be needed for a non-functional requirement, etc. In this classification, we relied on the primary, evident type of a requirement, without excluding the possibility of overlaps. The number of requirements allocated to each type emerged as follows:

Table 6. Requirements overview

Type of requirement	Number of requirements
---------------------	------------------------

¹⁶ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>

¹⁷ <https://eucoc.cloud/en/about/about-eu-cloud-coc>

Functional	46
Non-functional	37
Legal	97
Documentation	3

Categories - Moving down a level, we’ve further broken down the requirements into 27 categories. Each category indicates the primary area from which the requirement stems, even if overlaps appear and a single requirement could belong to multiple categories. The list of categories and number of requirements allocated to each emerged as follows:

Table 7. Requirements categorisation

Category of requirement	Number of requirements
Authentication & Authorization	11
Automation	1
Data agreement	3
Data discovery	1
Data quality	3
Data sharing	10
Documentation (inc. IPR and Security documents)	23
Efficiency	2
Feature	1
Federated Learning	2
General Requirements	4
Interoperability	14
Metadata	1
Monitoring & Traceability	6
Network	1
Non-linear operations	1
Performance & Sustainability	1
Requirement Content	1
Scalability	1
Security	20
Security & Maintainability	2
Security & Privacy	19
Security, Maintainability	1

Security/Logging	9
Technical	21
Usability	1
User Interface	4

It's interesting to note that the largest category of requirements is that of security-related elements (51), with a strong privacy component (19). Documentation is also a significant category (23), and so is that of technical requirements (21).

Subject matter - We've also classified requirements based on the subject matter they apply to, mostly distinguishing between technical components in this case. The list of subject matter types and number of requirements allocated to each emerged as follows:

Table 8. Requirements subject matter

Subject matter	Number of requirements
Audit System	9
Authentication Platform	1
Authentication System	3
Cryptographic System	2
Data	1
Data Agreement Management Platform	7
Data Sharing Platform	18
Documentation	29
Federated Learning Toolbox	3
Metadata Catalog	11
Requirements List	1
System	82
Trusted Execution Environment	6

It is evident that the subject matter pertaining to the highest number of requirements is the system in question (82). To an extent, this is justified by the fact that system is the core regulated matter within this deliverable; and often, it is more efficient and effective to anchor a requirement in the system, allowing its developers and/or operators to decide which element of the system they should act on in order to bring the requirement to life. The second subject matter in terms of requirement numbers is that of documentation (29) reflecting the contemporary role of appropriate documentation in accountability and compliance with frameworks developed with digital technologies in mind. Finally, it's also worth highlighting the third subject matter, data sharing platform (18); it underlines the importance and

sensitivity required towards data sharing solutions on both regulatory and public attention levels.

Justifications - We've drawn on multiple sources to develop the list of requirements. The corresponding list of justifications can be presented as follows:

- *EU legislation* - e.g., General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), AI Act, Cyber Resilience Act, Data Act, European Health Data Space Regulation (EHDS), eIDAS 2 Regulation
- *National legislation (primary and secondary)*
- *EU-wide guidelines and frameworks* - e.g., FAIR Open Access Principles
- *Standards from standardisation bodies* - e.g., W3C Verifiable Credentials
- *Consortium-established justifications* - e.g., steps needed in order to enhance security (unanchored to a specific framework); enable data sharing; support interoperability with European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

In terms of numbers, the justifications emerged as follows:

Table 9. Requirements justification

Justification	Number of requirements
GDPR	11
AI Act	1
Cyber Resilience Act	1
Data Act	15
EHDS Regulation (with EHR requirements)	51
European Digital Identity Framework	3
National laws	6
FAIR Open Access Principles	14
W3C Verifiable Credentials	1
Consortium-established	72

Taken together, the EU legislation group of justifications is the largest one (83). Within this group, it's interesting to note that the most visible instrument is the EHDS Regulation (51). This is due to the pioneering nature of EHDS as one of the most prominent and well-regulated data spaces in the EU.

4.3. Full legal, regulative, and ethical requirements table

The full requirements list is found within the documents Annex I. The list is correct as of the 25/10/2024 (M9).

The list has since been frozen, and the review process is being undertaken by task leads UKO and Fraunhofer ISST. This will continue until the next iteration of the requirements list is completed and submitted by M18 of the project.

5. Conclusions and next steps

The process for gathering legal and ethical requirements for TITAN provided 107 requirements, provided by all partners.

TRI will supplement requirements by deriving additional requirements from national legislations during the next phase of the project, as the use-cases are developed in greater detail. TRI will work with the use-case partners to elicit these additional requirements.

TRI will continue to work with the technical partners to understand how the legal requirements are reflected within the technical and non-technical requirements for the platform.

TRI will also continue to work with UKO on the second round of revisions for these requirements to ensure clarity, consistency, and avoid duplication.

ALL partners will continue to refine the requirements table with the oversight of UKO and Fraunhofer ISST. The final version of this will be delivered in M18 of the project.

Annex I

Legal, Regulatory, and Ethical Requirements

Igl-001

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Documentation Content / IPR
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	Documentation
Requirement Sentence	The documentation SHALL list the licenses of all the system's components and third party libraries the components depend on.
Justification	The usage (and/or modification) of software under certain licenses is permitted only, if the license and its conditions are mentioned.
Author	UKO
Responsible Task(s)	all
Source	Legal Experts
Comments	If the requirements of a certain license is considered to be too restrictive, the component under that license should be considered to be replaced.
Refers to	e.g. GPL3

Igl-002

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Documentation Content / IPR
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	Documentation
Requirement Sentence	IF an effective license requires to include copies of the license's full text, the documentation and/or source code SHALL contain a copy of the licence's full text.
Justification	The distribution of software under certain licenses is permitted only, if the license's full text is also part of the distribution.
Author	UKO
Responsible Task(s)	all
Source	Legal Experts
Comments	The copies of the licenses' full texts should be included in the electronic version of the documentation (if required) and/or source code.
Refers to	e.g. GPL3

Igl-003

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Interoperability and Open Standards
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Alignment with International Standards
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL comply with ISO standards for information security and data management.
Justification	Ensures adherence to internationally recognized standards for security and data management.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA, DSSC, EOSC-IF, GDPR

Igl-004

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Interoperability and Open Standards
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Alignment with International Standards
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL align with CEN/CENELEC standards to ensure compatibility with European data exchange requirements.
Justification	Ensures compliance with European standards for data interoperability.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA, DSSC, European Committee for Standardization (CEN), European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization (CENELEC)

Igl-005

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Interoperability and Open Standards
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Alignment with International Standards
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL implement W3C standards for web interoperability and data sharing.
Justification	Ensures adherence to web standards for data sharing and interoperability.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA, DSSC, EOSC-IF, W3C

Igl-006

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Data Security and Privacy
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Adherence to Data Protection Regulations
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL implement GDPR-compliant data processing mechanisms, including data pseudonymization and anonymization.
Justification	Ensures compliance with GDPR requirements for data protection.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA, EOSC-IF, GDPR

Igl-007

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Data Security and Privacy
Liability	WILL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Adherence to Data Protection Regulations
Requirement Sentence	The system WILL provide tools for data subjects to exercise their rights under GDPR, such as data access, rectification, and deletion.
Justification	Ensures users can exercise their rights under data protection laws.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA, EOSC-IF GDPR

Igl-008

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Federation and Decentralization
Liability	WILL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Multi-Party Trust Frameworks
Requirement Sentence	The system WILL establish a trust framework defining roles, responsibilities, and compliance rules for all participants.
Justification	Provides a clear and enforceable structure for governance and compliance.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA, EOSC-IF

Igl-009

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Transparency and Open Governance
Liability	WILL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Open Source Development
Requirement Sentence	The system WILL maintain an open repository for source code and documentation, ensuring transparency and collaborative development.
Justification	Encourages community involvement and continuous improvement through open-source development.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA, EOSC-IF

Igl-010

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Transparency and Open Governance
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Transparent Policies and Decision-Making
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL publish governance policies, rules, and decision-making processes in a publicly accessible manner.
Justification	Ensures transparency and stakeholder confidence in governance processes.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA

Igl-011

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Personal Data Handling
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Guidelines for Personal Data Handling
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL establish and document guidelines for handling personal data, ensuring compliance with relevant regulations.
Justification	Provides clear instructions to ensure regulatory compliance in personal data handling.
Author	UKO
Refers to	IDSA, EOSC-IF, GDPR

Igl-012

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Security & Privacy
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL ensure the privacy of individuals and sensitive data aligned with GDPR.
Justification	GDPR principles need to be enforced.
Author	UMU
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.1
Refers to	GDPR

Igl-013

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Data Privacy
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL ensure that individuals are informed about the use of their data and their rights under data protection laws.
Justification	Ensures that users are aware of how their information is used and of their rights.
Author	UMU
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.1
Refers to	EHDS

Igl-014

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Security & Privacy
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	All components SHALL conform to Act on the Secondary Use of Health and Social Data (in Finland).
Justification	It is legally required.
Author	UEF
Refers to	GDPR and Act on the Secondary Use of Health and Social Data

Igl-015

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Data Agreement
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Data Agreement Management Platform
Requirement Sentence	The Data Agreement Management Platform SHALL BE DESIGNED IN A WAY to follow the GDPR requirements from End-to-End of agreement life cycle.
Author	FUJ
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.1
Refers to	GDPR

Igl-016

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Security
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL record in a verifiable manner the purpose and legal basis for processing of personal data.
Justification	Transparency is a key principle of GDPR, ensuring individuals understand how their data is used.
Author	TRI
Refers to	Art 5.1 GDPR

Igl-017

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Security
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL only allow collection and further processing of personal data for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes.
Justification	Data minimisation ensures data is collected only for its intended use.
Author	TRI
Refers to	Art 5.1 GDPR

Igl-018

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Security
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHOULD collect and process the minimum amount of personal data necessary in relation to the purposes for which it is processed.
Justification	Minimising data collection reduces privacy risks and storage requirements.
Author	TRI
Refers to	Art 5.1 GDPR

Igl-019

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Security
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL BE ABLE TO pseudonymise personal data.
Justification	GDPR
Author	TRI
Refers to	GDPR

Igl-020

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Security
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL BE ABLE TO anonymise personal data after pseudonymisation.
Justification	GDPR
Author	TRI
Refers to	GDPR

Igl-021

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Security
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL store personal data in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data is processed.
Justification	Data retention periods should be defined and enforced to avoid unnecessary storage.
Author	TRI
Refers to	Art 5.1 GDPR

Igl-022

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Security
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL define data retention periods.
Justification	Personal data in a form which permits identification of data subjects should be stored for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data is processed.
Author	TRI
Refers to	Art 5.1 GDPR

Igl-023

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Security
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHOULD have automated processes to ensure data is not retained longer than the defined data retention period.
Justification	Personal data in a form which permits identification of data subjects should be stored for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data is processed.
Author	TRI
Comments	Depends on the length of the data retention period, may be irrelevant
Refers to	Art 5.1 GDPR

Igl-024

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Security
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL PROVIDE users WITH THE ABILITY TO request deletion of their personal data.
Justification	GDPR data retention principle
Author	TRI
Refers to	Art 5.1 GDPR

Igl-025

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Security
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	IF a data deletion request is received, the system SHALL verify the requestor's identity and initiate a secure deletion process.
Justification	GDPR data retention principle
Author	TRI
Refers to	Art 5.1 GDPR

Igl-026

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Security
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL log all data deletion activities.
Justification	GDPR data retention principle
Author	TRI
Refers to	Art 5.1 GDPR

Igl-027

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Security
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	-
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHOULD allow designation of a data controller and data processors for all datasets.
Author	TRI
Refers to	Art 5.1 GDPR

Igl-028

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Security
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL notify controller and processors when a data deletion request has been made by a data subject.
Justification	GDPR data retention principle
Author	TRI
Refers to	Art 5.1 GDPR

Igl-029

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Security
Liability	WILL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system WILL implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure a level of security appropriate to the risk.
Justification	Data security safeguards personal information from unauthorised access, disclosure, alteration, or destruction.
Author	TRI
Refers to	Art 5.1 GDPR

Igl-030

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Security
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	-
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHOULD enable the controller to demonstrate compliance with the principles of GDPR.
Justification	Accountability ensures the controller can demonstrate adherence to GDPR regulations.
Author	TRI
Refers to	Art 5.2 GDPR

Igl-031

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Interoperability
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Metadata Catalog
Requirement Sentence	The Metadata Catalog SHALL include clear and accessible data usage licenses.
Justification	FAIR Reusable
Author	TRI
Refers to	FAIR R1.1

Igl-032

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	General Requirements
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	EHR System
Requirement Sentence	The harmonised components of an electronic health record system (EHR system) SHALL achieve the performance intended by its manufacturer and SHALL be designed and manufactured in such a way that, during normal conditions of use, they are suitable for their intended purpose and their use does not put at risk patient safety.
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex II, 1.1)

Igl-033

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	General Requirements
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	EHR System
Requirement Sentence	The harmonised components of the EHR system SHALL be designed and developed in such a way that the system can be supplied and installed, taking into account the instructions and information provided by the manufacturer, without adversely affecting its characteristics and performance during its intended use.
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex II, 1.2)

Igl-034

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	General Requirements
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	EHR System
Requirement Sentence	An EHR system SHALL be designed and developed in such a way that its interoperability, safety and security features uphold the rights of natural persons, in line with the intended purpose of the EHR system, as set out in Chapter II of this Regulation.
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex II, 1.3) Please see technical requirements further down this list

Igl-035

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	General Requirements
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	EHR System
Requirement Sentence	The harmonised components of an EHR system that is intended to be operated together with other products, including medical devices, SHALL be designed and manufactured in such a way that interoperability and compatibility are reliable and secure, and personal electronic health data can be shared between the device and the EHR system in relation to those two components.
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex II, 1.4)

Igl-036

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Interoperability
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	EHR System
Requirement Sentence	Where an EHR system is designed to store or intermediate personal electronic health data, it SHALL provide an interface enabling access to the personal electronic health data processed by it in the European health record exchange format, by means of the European interoperability component for EHR systems.
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex II, 2.1.a)

Igl-037

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Interoperability
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	EHR System
Requirement Sentence	Where an EHR system is designed to store or intermediate personal electronic health data, it SHALL be able to receive personal electronic health data in the European health record exchange format, by means of the European interoperability component for EHR systems.
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex II, 2.1.b)

Igl-038

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Interoperability
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	EHR System
Requirement Sentence	An EHR system that includes a functionality for entering structured personal electronic health data SHALL enable the entry of data with granularity sufficient to enable the provision of the entered personal electronic health data in the European health record exchange format.
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex II, 2.3)

Igl-039

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Interoperability
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	EHR System
Requirement Sentence	The harmonised components of an EHR system SHALL NOT include features that prohibit, restrict or place undue burden on authorised access, personal electronic health data sharing, or use of personal electronic health data for permitted purposes.
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex II, 2.4)

Igl-040

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Interoperability
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	EHR System
Requirement Sentence	The harmonised components of an EHR system SHALL NOT include features that prohibit, restrict or place undue burden on authorised exporting of personal electronic health data for the reasons of replacing the EHR system by another product.
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex II, 2.5)

Igl-041

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Security/Logging
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	EHR System
Requirement Sentence	An EHR system designed to be used by health professionals SHALL provide reliable mechanisms for the identification and authentication of health professionals.
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex II, 3.2) Please see "Article 9 Identification management" of EHDS

Igl-042

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Security/Logging
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	EHR System
Requirement Sentence	The harmonised logging component of an EHR system designed to enable access by health providers or other individuals to personal electronic health data SHALL provide sufficient logging mechanisms that record at least the following information on every access event or group of events: a) identification of the health provider or other individuals having accessed personal electronic health data;
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex II, 3.4.a)

Igl-043

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Security/Logging
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	EHR System
Requirement Sentence	The harmonised logging component of an EHR system designed to enable access by health providers or other individuals to personal electronic health data SHALL provide sufficient logging mechanisms that record at least the following information on every access event or group of events: b) identification of the specific individual or individuals having accessed personal electronic health data;
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex II, 3.4.b)

Igl-044

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Security/Logging
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	EHR System
Requirement Sentence	The harmonised logging component of an EHR system designed to enable access by health providers or other individuals to personal electronic health data SHALL provide sufficient logging mechanisms that record at least the following information on every access event or group of events: c) categories of data accessed;
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex II, 3.4.c)

Igl-045

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Security/Logging
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	EHR System
Requirement Sentence	The harmonised logging component of an EHR system designed to enable access by health providers or other individuals to personal electronic health data SHALL provide sufficient logging mechanisms that record at least the following information on every access event or group of events: d) time and date accessed;
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex II, 3.4.d)

Igl-046

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Security/Logging
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	EHR System
Requirement Sentence	The harmonised logging component of an EHR system designed to enable access by health providers or other individuals to personal electronic health data SHALL provide sufficient logging mechanisms that record at least the following information on every access event or group of events: e) origin(s) of data;
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex II, 3.4.e)

Igl-047

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Security/Logging
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	EHR System
Requirement Sentence	The harmonised components of an EHR system SHALL include tools or mechanisms to review and analyse the log data, OR it SHALL support the connection and use of external software for the same purposes.
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex II, 3.6)

Igl-048

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Security/Logging
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	EHR System
Requirement Sentence	The harmonised components of an EHR system that store personal electronic health data SHALL support different retention periods and access rights that take into account the origins and categories of electronic health data.
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex II, 3.8)

Igl-049

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Documentation
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Documentation
Requirement Sentence	<p>The technical documentation referred to in Article 24 SHALL contain at least the following information, as applicable to the harmonised components of EHR systems in the relevant EHR system:</p> <p>A detailed description of the EHR system including:</p> <p>a) its intended purpose, the date and the version of the EHR system;</p>
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex III, 1.a)

Igl-050

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Documentation
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Documentation
Requirement Sentence	<p>The technical documentation referred to in Article 24 SHALL contain at least the following information, as applicable to the harmonised components of EHR systems in the relevant EHR system:</p> <p>A detailed description of the EHR system including:</p> <p>b) the categories of personal electronic health data that the EHR system has been designed to process;</p>
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex III, 1.b)

Igl-051

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Documentation
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Documentation
Requirement Sentence	<p>The technical documentation referred to in Article 24 SHALL contain at least the following information, as applicable to the harmonised components of EHR systems in the relevant EHR system:</p> <p>A detailed description of the EHR system including:</p> <p>(c) how the EHR system interacts or can be used to interact with hardware or software that is not part of the EHR system itself;</p>
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex III, 1.c)

Igl-052

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Documentation
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Documentation
Requirement Sentence	<p>The technical documentation referred to in Article 24 SHALL contain at least the following information, as applicable to the harmonised components of EHR systems in the relevant EHR system:</p> <p>A detailed description of the EHR system including:</p> <p>(d) the versions of relevant software or firmware and any requirement related to version update;</p>
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex III, 1.d)

Igl-053

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Documentation
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Documentation
Requirement Sentence	<p>The technical documentation referred to in Article 24 SHALL contain at least the following information, as applicable to the harmonised components of EHR systems in the relevant EHR system:</p> <p>A detailed description of the EHR system including:</p> <p>(e) the description of all forms in which the EHR system is placed on the market or put into service;</p>
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex III, 1.e)

Igl-054

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Documentation
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Documentation
Requirement Sentence	<p>The technical documentation referred to in Article 24 SHALL contain at least the following information, as applicable to the harmonised components of EHR systems in the relevant EHR system:</p> <p>A detailed description of the EHR system including:</p> <p>(f) the description of hardware on which the EHR system is intended to run;</p>
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex III, 1.f)

Igl-055

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Documentation
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Documentation
Requirement Sentence	<p>The technical documentation referred to in Article 24 SHALL contain at least the following information, as applicable to the harmonised components of EHR systems in the relevant EHR system:</p> <p>A detailed description of the EHR system including:</p> <p>(g) a description of the system architecture explaining how software components build on or feed into each other and integrate into the overall processing, including where appropriate, labelled pictorial representations (e.g. diagrams and drawings), clearly indicating key parts/components and including sufficient explanation to understand the drawings and diagrams;</p>
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex III, 1.g)

Igl-056

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Documentation
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Documentation
Requirement Sentence	<p>The technical documentation referred to in Article 24 SHALL contain at least the following information, as applicable to the harmonised components of EHR systems in the relevant EHR system:</p> <p>A detailed description of the EHR system including:</p> <p>(h) the technical specifications, such as features, dimensions and performance attributes, of the EHR system and any variants/configurations and accessories that would typically appear in the product specification made available to the user, for example in brochures, catalogues and similar publications, including a detailed description of the data structures, storage and input/output of data;</p>
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex III, 1.h)

Igl-057

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Documentation
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Documentation
Requirement Sentence	<p>The technical documentation referred to in Article 24 SHALL contain at least the following information, as applicable to the harmonised components of EHR systems in the relevant EHR system:</p> <p>A detailed description of the EHR system including:</p> <p>(i) a description of any change made to the system throughout its lifecycle;</p>
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex III, 1.i)

Igl-058

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Documentation
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Documentation
Requirement Sentence	<p>The technical documentation referred to in Article 24 SHALL contain at least the following information, as applicable to the harmonised components of EHR systems in the relevant EHR system:</p> <p>A detailed description of the EHR system including:</p> <p>(j) the instructions of use for the user and, where applicable, installation instructions.</p>
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex III, 1.j)

Igl-059

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Documentation
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Documentation
Requirement Sentence	<p>The technical documentation referred to in Article 24 SHALL contain at least the following information, as applicable to the harmonised components of EHR systems in the relevant EHR system:</p> <p>A detailed description of the system in place to evaluate the EHR system performance, where applicable.</p>
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex III, 2)

Igl-060

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Documentation
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Documentation
Requirement Sentence	<p>The technical documentation referred to in Article 24 SHALL contain at least the following information, as applicable to the harmonised components of EHR systems in the relevant EHR system:</p> <p>The references to any common specification used in accordance with Article 23 and in relation to which conformity is declared.</p>
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex III, 3)

Igl-061

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Documentation
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Documentation
Requirement Sentence	<p>The technical documentation referred to in Article 24 SHALL contain at least the following information, as applicable to the harmonised components of EHR systems in the relevant EHR system:</p> <p>The results and critical analyses of all verifications and validation tests undertaken to demonstrate conformity of the EHR system with the requirements laid down in Chapter III of this Regulation, in particular the applicable essential requirements.</p>
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex III, 4)

Igl-062

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Documentation
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Documentation
Requirement Sentence	The documentation SHALL include a copy of the information sheet referred to in Article 25.
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex III, 5)

Igl-063

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Documentation
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Documentation
Requirement Sentence	The documentation SHALL include a copy of the EU declaration of conformity.
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Interoperability
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Annex III, 6) Please see Article 26

Igl-064

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Technical
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL allow natural persons to access their electronic health data immediately after the personal electronic health data has been registered in an EHR system, adhering to technological practicability, free of charge and in an easily readable, consolidated and accessible form.
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Conformity/Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Article 8(a))

Igl-065

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Technical
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL allow natural persons to download a copy of their electronic health data free of charge.
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Conformity/Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Article 8(b))

Igl-066

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Technical
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL have one or more proxy services established to ensure quality of service.
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Conformity/Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Article 8(g)(2))

Igl-067

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Technical
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Proxy Services
Requirement Sentence	The system's proxy services SHALL provide authorisations in a transparent and easily understandable way, free of charge, electronically or on paper.
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Conformity/Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Article 8(g)(2)(aa))

Igl-068

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Technical
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Proxy Services
Requirement Sentence	The system's proxy services SHALL provide a complaint mechanism for natural persons.
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Conformity/Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Article 8(g)(2)(aa))

Igl-069

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Technical
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Proxy Services
Requirement Sentence	The system's proxy services SHALL be interoperable among Member States.
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Conformity/Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Article 8(g)(2)(a))

Igl-070

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Technical
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Proxy Services
Requirement Sentence	The system and the proxy services SHALL be easily accessible for persons with disabilities, vulnerable groups or persons with low digital literacy.
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Conformity/Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Article 8(g)(2)(b))

Igl-071

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Technical
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL allow natural persons or their representatives to insert information in their own electronic health record through electronic health data access services or applications linked to these services.
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Conformity/Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Article 8(b)(1))

Igl-072

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Technical
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	<p>The system SHALL allow natural persons or their representatives as referred to in Article 8g(2) to insert information in their own electronic health records through electronic health data access services.</p> <p>The system SHALL clearly distinguish data as inserted by the natural person or by his or her representative.</p>
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Conformity/Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Article 8(b)(1))

Igl-073

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Technical
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL not allow natural persons to have the possibility to directly alter the electronic health data and related information inserted by health professionals.
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Conformity/Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Article 8(b)(1))

Igl-074

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Technical
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL provide a possibility for natural persons to easily request rectification of their personal data online as a way to exercise their right to rectification under Article 16 of Regulation (EU) 2016/679.
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Conformity/Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Article 8(c)(3))

Igl-075

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Technical
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL allow natural persons to give access to or request a healthcare provider to transmit all or part of their electronic health data to another healthcare provider of their choice immediately, free of charge and without hindrance from the health care provider or from the manufacturers of the systems used by that healthcare provider
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Conformity/Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Article 8(d)(1))

Igl-076

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Technical
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL be able to transmit a part of a natural person's electronic health data to a clearly identified recipient in the social security or reimbursement services sector, immediately, free of charge and without hindrance from the healthcare provider or from the manufacturers of the systems used by that healthcare provider. Such a transmission SHALL be one-way only.
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Conformity/Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Article 8(d)(3))

Igl-077

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Technical
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	<p>The system SHALL allow natural persons to obtain information, including through automatic notifications, on any access to their personal electronic health data.</p> <p>The information SHALL be provided without delay and free of charge through electronic health data access services.</p> <p>The information SHALL be available for at least three years after each data access.</p> <p>The information SHALL include, at least, the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) the healthcare provider or other individuals who accessed the personal electronic health data; (b) the date and time of access; (c) the personal electronic health data that was accessed.
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Conformity/Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Article 8(f))

Igl-078

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Technical
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL facilitate a natural person to exercise their right to opt out from anyone accessing their personal electronic health data registered in an EHR system through the electronic health data access services. This feature SHALL be reversible.
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Conformity/Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Article 8(h))

Igl-079

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Documentation
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Documentation
Requirement Sentence	<p>The system SHALL be accompanied by an information sheet that includes concise, complete, correct and clear information that is relevant, accessible and comprehensible to professional users.</p> <p>The information sheet referred to in paragraph 1 shall specify:</p> <p>(a) the identity, registered trade name or registered trademark, and the contact details of the manufacturer and, where applicable, of its authorised representative;</p> <p>(b) the name and version of the EHR system and date of its release;</p> <p>(c) its intended purpose;</p> <p>(d) the categories of electronic health data that the EHR system has been designed to process;</p> <p>(e) the standards, formats and specifications and versions thereof supported by the EHR system.</p> <p>As an alternative to supplying the information sheet referred to in paragraph 1 with the system, manufacturers may enter the information referred to in paragraph 2 into the EU database referred to in Article 32.</p>
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Conformity/Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Article 25)

Igl-080

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Documentation
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Documentation
Requirement Sentence	<p>The system SHALL have a CE marking affixed visibly, legibly and indelibly to the accompanying documents of the EHR system and, where applicable, to the packaging.</p> <p>1a. The CE marking shall be affixed before placing the EHR system on the market.</p> <p>2. The CE marking shall be subject to the general principles set out in Article 30 of Regulation (EC) 765/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council.</p>
Justification	EHDS/EHR System Conformity/Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/
Refers to	Proposal for EHDS (Compromise Text - Article 27)

Igl-081

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Technical
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHOULD allow 'connected products' to connect and upload data to the platform. A 'connected product' means an item that obtains, generates or collects data concerning its use or environment and that is able to communicate product data via an electronic communications service, physical connection or on-device access, and whose primary function is not the storing, processing or transmission of data on behalf of any party other than the user;
Justification	Data Act Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/2854
Refers to	Data Act Article 3(1)

Igl-082

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Technical
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHOULD allow access to the 'connected product' data to the user, where technically feasible.
Justification	Data Act Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/2854
Refers to	Data Act Article 3(1)

Igl-083

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Technical
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL allow the confidentiality of trade secrets to be maintained.
Justification	Data Act Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/2854
Refers to	Data Act Article 4(6)

Igl-084

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Technical
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL allow access to data by a nominated third party, if required to do so by request of the user.
Justification	Data Act Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/2854
Refers to	Data Act Article 5(1)

Igl-085

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Technical
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL allow erasure of data made available by the data holder, and any copies thereof.
Justification	Data Act Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/2854
Refers to	Data Act Article 11(2)(a)

Igl-086

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Technical
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL allow temporary and time limited access to data, for exceptional purposes.
Justification	Data Act Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/2854
Refers to	Data Act Article 15

Igl-087

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Technical
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL allow sufficient description of metadata such as information on dataset content, use restrictions, licences, data collection methodology, data quality and uncertainty to be included, in a machine-readable format, to allow the recipient to find, access and use the data.
Justification	Data Act Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/2854
Refers to	Data Act Article 33(1)(a)

Igl-088

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Technical
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Documentation
Requirement Sentence	The documentation SHALL describe in a publicly available and consistent manner the data structures, data formats, vocabularies, classification schemes, taxonomies and code lists, where available.
Justification	Data Act Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/2854
Refers to	Data Act Article 33(1)(b)

Igl-089

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Technical
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Documentation
Requirement Sentence	The documentation SHALL sufficiently describe the technical means to access the data, such as application programming interfaces, and their terms of use and quality of service to enable automatic access and transmission of data between parties, including continuously, in bulk download or in real-time in a machine-readable format where that is technically feasible and does not hamper the good functioning of the connected product;
Justification	Data Act Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/2854
Refers to	Data Act Article 33(1)(c)

Igl-090

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Technical
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Documentation
Requirement Sentence	The documentation SHALL provide the means to enable the interoperability of tools for automating the execution of data sharing agreements, such as smart contracts, where applicable.
Justification	Data Act Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/2854
Refers to	Data Act Article 33(1)(d)

Igl-091

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Technical
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL include a smart contract that is designed to offer access control mechanisms and a very high degree of robustness to avoid functional errors and to withstand manipulation by third parties.
Justification	Data Act Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/2854
Refers to	Data Act Article 36(1)(a)

Igl-092

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Technical
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL include a mechanism to terminate the continued execution of transactions in relation to the smart contract and that the smart contract includes internal functions which can reset or instruct the contract to stop or interrupt the operation, in particular to avoid future accidental executions.
Justification	Data Act Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/2854
Refers to	Data Act Article 36(1)(b)

Igl-093

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Technical
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL, in circumstances in which a smart contract must be terminated or deactivated, include the possibility to archive the transactional data, smart contract logic and code in order to keep the record of operations performed on the data in the past for auditability.
Justification	Data Act Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/2854
Refers to	Data Act Article 36(1)(c)

Igl-094

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Technical
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL ensure that a smart contract is protected through rigorous access control mechanisms at the governance and smart contract layers.
Justification	Data Act Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/2854
Refers to	Data Act Article 36(1)(d)

Igl-095

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Technical
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL ensure consistency with the terms of the data sharing agreement that the smart contract executes.
Justification	Data Act Compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/2854
Refers to	Data Act Article 36(1)(e)

Igl-096

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Technical
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL inform any person exposed to the system in a timely, clear manner when interacting with an AI system, unless obvious from context.
Justification	AI Act Transparency
Author	TRI
Comments	https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/TA-9-2024-0138-FNL-COR01_EN.pdf
Refers to	AI Act Compliance

Igl-097

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Documentation
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Documentation
Requirement Sentence	The documentation SHALL include a cybersecurity risk assessment.
Justification	Cyber Resilience Act Article 13 (3)
Author	TRI
Comments	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52022PC0454
Refers to	CRA Act Compliance

Igl-098

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Documentation
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL not prohibit users to identify themselves by a pseudonym when accessing the system, unless prohibited by Union or national legislation.
Justification	eIDAS 2 (EDIF) compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1183/oj
Refers to	EDI Framework Article (5)

Igl-099

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Documentation
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHOUD provide identification and authorisation interoperability with European Identity Wallets.
Justification	eIDAS 2 (EDIF) compliance
Author	TRI
Comments	http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1183/oj
Refers to	EDI Framework Article (5a)(4)(a)

Igl-100

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Security
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	All components SHALL conform to German law.
Justification	It is legally required.
Author	CHA

Igl-101

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	-
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Documentation
Requirement Sentence	Jardé Law - 3 research categories
Justification	Category 1 research also requires mandatory authorization from the French National Agency for the Safety of Medicines and Health Products (ANSM). For Category 2 and 3 research, the ANSM is simply notified of the ethics committee opinion, without its authorization being required.
Author	INS
Source	DPO/IRB/CNIL
Comments	recherche impliquant la personne humaine
Refers to	GDPR

Igl-102

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	-
Liability	-
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Documentation
Requirement Sentence	National Commission for Information Technology and Liberties
Author	INS
Source	CNIL
Comments	the CNIL organizes public debates around new digital issues, at the intersection of field and scientific expertise.
Refers to	GDPR/EOSC

Igl-103

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	-
Liability	-
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Documentation
Requirement Sentence	Le Comité européen de la protection des données (CEPD)
Author	INS
Source	CEPD
Refers to	GDPR

Igl-104

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Security
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	All components SHALL conform to French law.
Justification	It is legally required.
Author	INS

Igl-105

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Security
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	All components SHALL conform to Italian law.
Justification	It is legally required

Igl-106

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Security
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	All components SHALL conform to Spanish law.
Justification	It is legally required

Igl-107

Aspect	Content
Type	Legal
Category	Metadata
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	Data Sharing Platform
Requirement Sentence	Subsystem providing access to data sets (raw or transformed) obtained from some data sources (e.g., SIAR climatic stations, AEMET climatic stations, COPERNICUS-?-) must explicitly recognise the sources of the data, although they can be used for free. To be included as metadata in the dataset's descriptions?